

Recurrence Plots of Coronavirus Daily New Cases

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The web site worldometer, <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>, is giving data about Covid-19 Coronavirus Pandemic. For each country, the site is showing, among several graphs, those of the daily new cases, from February 15 to the day of the visualization of the page. A 7-day moving average is also displayed for data. Here we show recurrence plots of such averaged daily new cases concerning some countries (Italy, Germany, Spain, France, United Kingdom, Sweden, Israel and Japan).

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Actually all these data can be considered as time series. These series are commonly used in signal processing [1]. They are consisting of sequences of data measured typically at successive points, which are spaced at uniform time intervals. Time series can be analysed using frequency-domain and time-domain methods: the former includes spectral analysis, the latter autocorrelation and cross-correlation analysis. Among the methods based on the time-domain, we find the recurrence plots. These plots are displaying the recurrence of states of the dynamical system, that is, states that are arbitrarily close again after some time of divergence.

In 1987, Eckmann, Kamphorst and Ruelle proposed the recurrence plots to visualise the recurrence of states in phase spaces with an arbitrary number of dimensions [2,3]. These plots enabled to see the phase space trajectories through a two-dimensional representation of its recurrences. A recurrence at a different time j of a state observed at time i was depicted within a two-dimensional squared black and white image, with black dots marking recurrences. Both axes of the image were time axes. The resulting image was depending on a threshold distance, which was determining the nearer states in the phase space. Nowadays, several tools are freely available to have the recurrence plots from data files, using colours and different layouts to represent distances between the states. Here, we will use the tool developed by E. Kononov, www.visualization-2002.org/. In the images here proposed, the white pixels are marking the recurrences.

As discussed in [4], a recurrence plot is not depending on the scale factor, which we use to describe the phase space states. Then if we have to plot the recurrence of a time series, the resulting plot will be the same for any scale factor or shift of the signal. For this reason, we can use recurrence plots to compare time series coming from different instruments as, for instance, in the case given in [4], provided their origin is in the same dynamical system. For this reason, here we propose the recurrence plots to visualize the data from <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>, in particular those of the daily new cases, from February 15 to 25 September, filtered by a 7-day moving average. Here, in the following images, the recurrence plots of such averaged daily new cases concerning Italy, Germany, Spain, France, United Kingdom, Sweden, Israel and Japan.

Recurrence plots for coronavirus daily cases from worldometer, 7-days average. On the two axes we have the days of observations. The data given in dark colours are representing large variations of the counts. The bright colours are representing small variations and therefore a recurrence. On the left, it is shown the plot for data from Germany and on the right from Italy. Note a small shift of the peaks and the broader peak for Italy. On the right, the scale of colours is given, ranging from 0 to the largest difference of values concerning the daily counts.

Here the graphs from worldometer for comparing time series and their representation by means of the recurrence plots.

Spain

France

Recurrence plots for Spain and France as previously done for Germany and Italy. Note the recurrence plot of Spain, which is showing the two peaks in the plot of the daily count. The coloured area, representing the behaviour of the recent peak appears to have passed its highest value. For France, the values of the first peak and of the last month are quite different. From the image, it is clear that the second peak has not yet reached its highest value. In the following image, the graphs from worldometer are given for comparing time series and their representation by means of the recurrence plots.

UK

Sweden

Recurrence plots for United Kingdom and Sweden. In UK, the second peak started. Note the quite different behaviour.

Israel

Japan

Here the plots for Israel and Japan. Both plots could be compared to the case of France, but, in Japan, the country has already passed the second peak.

In the previously given plots, we can find a different visualization of the time series. The resulting plots turn out to be represented in the same manner according to their scale factors. For this reason, we can compare the plots, without scaling the graphs according to their absolute numbers.

References

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